

A Content Analysis of Vision and Mission of Private Universities in Mogadishu in the Light of Competitive Advantages

Dr. Said Abubakar Sheikh Ahmed

An Associate Professor in Curriculum and Head of Research Department at Mogadishu University

Email: baashaa4@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims at analyzing the vision and mission of eleven private universities run in Mogadishu based on their competitive advantages. Quantitative analysis was applied where the author used coding in QDA MINER.LITE 1.4.1 for data analysis under three categories reflected by the content of the vision and mission posted on their official website, namely; Academic & Research, Values & Culture, and Social Need & Development. Each category has a sub-category. The results of the study generally showed that the non-competitive advantages of the universities 71% while competitive advantages scored up 29%. The study also explored that the most competitive advantages of the universities concentrated on the dimensions: values & culture and social needs & development. Besides, there is a variance among the universities regarding their non-competitive advantages and competitive advantages. Finally, the study recommends enhancing the quality of the statement strategies of the vision and mission for the private universities in Mogadishu in line with national and international standards.

Key Words: Analysis, Vision, Mission, Private Universities, Mogadishu, Competitive Advantages

Introduction

Before the downfall of the Somali central government, Somalia has only a single university; Somali National University controlled by the central government. When the central government collapsed in 1991, an educational gap emerged due to the civil war in this period, as the government's role in providing educational services in its various stages was absent. Early 1992 was when Somali academics determined to recover the education sector of the country to provide the education service that Somali people used to get from the central government that became not functioning at all. Education umbrellas, privately owned schools, institutes, and higher education institutions have

been established to fill the education service gap that the ministry of education was providing before 1991. (Plan, 2011).

During this period, the Somali diaspora, international NGOs, and Islamic aid agencies, have made a significant contribution to the rehabilitation and development of the education sector. (*The State of Higher Education in Somalia: Privatization, rapid growth, and the need for regulation*, 2013).

The tertiary education as privately owned universities was the tedious work for private sector educators. Nevertheless, the community-initiated academic establishments are making tremendous contributions to the higher education sector, particularly in the absence of an effective national government. These initiatives need to be commended as well as appreciated as milestones of achievement realized through community effort and sacrifice. Therefore, the foundation of these initiatives should not be exposed to factors that can fracture it if other matters necessary for the improvement of higher education are not enhanced along with what has already been achieved. (Eno, A. M., Mweseli, N.W.M., & Eno, 2015).

There are efforts of private universities leaderships to enhance the quality of education in accordance with the international standards. Based on that, the Ministry for Education, Culture, and Higher Education has a strategy Plan 2018-2020 for tertiary education include increasing youth/adult enrollment, quality standards, establishing higher education commission, and strengthening the research capacities. (By, 2020). Currently, Somali Higher Education Commission is engaging an assessment on tertiary education to determine the quality assurance of the universities in terms of administrative and academic standards. This assessment leded universities administration to engage elaborate works to review on their education systems to bring into line of the required standards. The author, as one of the Somali academics involved to the private education at all level, aims this work to explore the extent of vision and mission of the private universities in Mogadishu city to meet their competitive advantages. Beforehand, the author published an evaluation study on macro- environment of the private universities in Mogadishu from the view of lecturers and education experts, using PESTEL analysis and AHP. All these studies aim solely

to provide suggestions on improving the quality education standards of private universities.

Concept of Vision and Mission

Vision is future-oriented and defines where an organization might want to be situated in the market in 5, 10, 15, or 20 years'. It is a goal state embodying a long-term ambition of where an organization would like to be in the future relative to its competitors while Mission is the pursuit of a goal that is unique to an organization's competitive advantage(Heath et al., 2018).

Vision is a future image of the organization, as a fundamental factor which reflects a clear comprehension of the present situation and the future aimed. Vision is not the dreams that cannot be reached, yet it is the mind's realistic, earthly eye which organizes how and by what means the desired future situation can ideally be realized. (Altiok, 2011). Vision is an image of how we see our purpose unfolding or the preferred future we seek to create or to the question "What do we really want?". (Pane et al., 2018).

A mission is a clear, concise and enduring statement of the reasons for an organization's existence today. A vision represents future purpose, providing a mental picture of the aspirational existence that an organization is working toward(Horwath, 2005).

Mission reflects the way in which vision can be transformed into a tangible existence for the company. (Brătianu & Bălănescu, 2008).

Vision statements are an important element of strategic planning. It is defined as "a look towards the unknown to define the future, which combines current facts, hopes, dreams, threats and opportunities". (Ozdem, 2011).

A vision statement addresses the question "Where do we want to go"? whereas a mission statement addresses the question "Why do we exist ? (Heath et al., 2018). The mission statement is a brief description of the organization's fundamental purpose and answers the question, "Why do we exist?". (AchieveIt, 2014).

Vision Statement: a mental picture of what you want to accomplish or achieve.
Mission Statement: a general statement of how the vision will be achieved. The mission statement is an action statement that usually begins with the word "to". (Hofstrand, 2016).

Competitive Advantage

Competition is seen as a rivalry in a given field where each participant is guided by a quest for supremacy. (Dimitrova & Dimitrova, 2017).

The competitiveness of a company is defined as a level of competency with regard to other competitors by the following parameters: technology, staff knowledge, and skills, the level of strategic and operational planning, quality of management systems, production, and products, communication. (Kireeva et al., 2018).

Competition is at the core of the success or failure of firms. Competition determines the appropriateness of a firm's activities that can contribute to its performance, such as innovations, a cohesive culture, or good implementation. Competitive strategy is the search for a favorable competitive position in an industry, the fundamental arena in which competition occurs.(Mishra, 2017).

The term competitive advantage is the ability gained through various attributes and different level resources to perform at a higher level than others in the same industry or market. (Braslina et al., 2014).

Competitive Advantages: The competitive advantage considering one of the components of the organization marketing strategy which consist from a mixture of things tangible and non- tangible. Any organization can be owned a competitive advantage if it used the resources available and its capabilities in the right investment opportunities in the market. (Diab, 2013)

Vision and Mission of Somali Ministry for Education, Culture and Higher Education,

Vision statement. Fulfil the right of every Somali to education and build an adequate, well educated, better skilled and competent workforce that contributes to the spiritual, economic and human development of the nation. Mission statement. To ensure equitable access to inclusive, life-long quality education and training for all Somali citizens, through the sustained implementation and resourcing of a comprehensive Education Policy and Sector Strategic Plan.(Ministry of Education Culture and Higher education Somalia, 2017)

Table (1) Visions and Missions of Private Universities in Mogadishu

Universities	Vision	Mission
Mogadishu University (MU, 2020)	To be the premier non-state and non-profit university in Somalia, dedicated to provide affordable and accessible high quality education attuned to the national values of the Somali people.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To instil hope in the Somali society impaired by the collapsed state institutions and civil war, and revitalize community- basedinitiatives. • To educate and nurture creative generations committed to peace, good governance and Community services. • To encourage intellectual and scholarly developments, and foster openness to a wide range of ideas. • To deliver high quality education and research. • To improve Learning environments in line with international standards. • To integrate social and Islamic values, scientific knowledge, and technical skills required for sustainable development of Somalia.

SIMAD University (SU, 2020)	SU strives “to become a leading center of academic and professional excellence and virtue”.	SU provides high quality education, research and community services with the commitment of excellence, integrity, and professionalism. The university produces competent scholars and leaders of high quality and moral uprightness
Benadir University (BU, 2020)	<p>Benadir University vision is to position itself to meet the demands of a rapidly transforming community, in delivering a dynamic learning environment. BU prepares those it serves to meet the obligations inherent in being productive and responsible citizens and steward of our community.</p> <p>Benadir University intends to be a premier university that prepares students for life and work. Benadir University seeks to create opportunities through which people’s abilities, talents and creativity can in full expression. We aspire to world where people can promote their live in a manner of their own choice. We recognize that development today must safeguard the option of future generation. In the years ahead, the university will strive for excellence and prepare change. The University will realize, as situation where needs of the target population are addressed through long-term sustainable education program.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing modern education through work – based learning with collaborative teaching methodology. • Delivering systematic education guided by principles and values that preserve and sustain the local economy and the environment. • Produce graduates that embody competence, leadership, and moral integrity. • Constantly seek to improve the learning environment for students and their university experience.
Jazeera University (JU, 2020)	The vision of Jazeera University is to be a vibrant, all-encompassing and competitive Centre of excellence in education, learning, research and service to humanity.	Mission of Jazeera University is to provide excellent quality education and teaching, promote scholarship, service, innovation and ingenuity and instill ethical traits for sustainable personality.
University of Somalia (UNISO, 2020)	We envision creating a functional, competitive and research-based university which is responsive to the needs of the society through delivering world- class education and knowledge which prepare our students.	To strategically place the University of Somalia in an academically refined environment where research is a premier goal and in which development, innovation, and knowledge transfer through effective.

Jamhuriya University (JUST, 2020)	To become a university of international reputation and a distinguished institution of higher learning in research and innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To contribute to the advancement of knowledge and learning through research and education; To produce graduates who meet the expectations of the nation; To develop innovative and responsible leaders who are capable of dealing with changes in the global environment
Somalia International University (SUI, 2020)	SIU aspires to be the leading source of the country's brightest, most skillful, and ethical professionals and managers.	SIU is committed to the advancement of learning through teaching, research and service to society, and to produce qualified, capable, and morally sound graduates through educational excellence
City University (CU, 2020)	City University of Mogadishu will strive to become the preeminent leader in instruction, research, and service of society in Somalia and the region, and will pursue international recognition through excellence and rigorous standards.	Our primary mission is to educate morally upright, capable leaders equipped with relevant knowledge and transferable high skills to achieve their professional goals and offer leadership and service to their society and nation. Through quality assured excellence in instruction, research, and service, the university seeks to promote the well-being of the Somali people and contribute to the development of the nation, the continent, and our increasingly interconnected world.
Hormuud University (HU, 2020)	Hormuud University aims at becoming unique national center in education for engineering and other scientific specialist.	Providing quality education through the support and development of suitable academic environment for the benefit of the nation and Humanity.
Islamic University (IU, 2020)	The vision of Islamic university is to become one of the best universities locally and regionally and to produce effective and capable competencies in developing their society and nation as a whole.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To spread knowledge, culture, high values and ideals of Islamic civilization; To provide an exceptional education service in the field of higher education and scientific research; To deliver science, knowledge, skills and experiences in the best possible means so as to produce a well-qualified, and well efficient manpower who are capable to meet development requirements of the nations through creativity and continuous improvement
Plasma University (PU, 2020)	To be a leading world class university in East Africa that provides quality education relevant to the welfare of the society.	To prepare the next generation of skilled and ethical professionals by providing High quality education and training appropriate for the context of the nation.

The table above reveals that the most statement strategies of the private universities are analogous, but there are differences in some statements distributed in some universities as competitive advantages. However, the visions and missions of the above private universities are in line with the vision and mission of the Somali Minister for Education, Culture, and Higher Education.

Aim of the Study

The main aim of this study is to analyze the vision and mission of private universities in Mogadishu in light of their competitive advantages.

Specifically, this study seeks:

1. To determine the extent of the statement strategies of the vision and mission for the private universities in Mogadishu to be a competitive advantage.
2. To compare the level of the competitive advantage and non-competitive advantage of statement strategies stated in the vision and mission of the private universities in Mogadishu.

Methodology

This study is a qualitative analysis of the content of vision and mission of the private universities in Mogadishu. The author purposively selected 11 universities due to the availability of their documents in open access. Based on similarities and differences of the statement strategies among universities, the author categorized them into three dimensions (i.e. Academic & research, values & ethics and social needs & development), whereas each dimension has a sub-category. The dimension of the academic & research has six sub-categories. The dimension of the values & ethics contains four sub-categories. The dimension of the social need & development encompasses five sub-categories. The author coded all these categories and sub-categories as illustrated in table (1). For the data analysis, the author used frequency and percentage in QDA MINER.LITE 1.4.1.

Table .2.The Study Dimensions, Codes, and their Indicators

Dimensions	Codes	Indicators	Dimensions	Codes	Indicators	Dimensions	Codes	Indicators
Academic and Research(AR)	PI	Premier Institution	Value and Culture (VC)	NV	National Values	Social Needs and Development (SND)	CS	Social service
	QE	Quality Education		IV	Islamic Values		OI	Open ideas
	QR	Quality Research		H	Humanity		PG	Peace &Governance
	ASC	Abilities, Skills and Creativity		EP	Ethical professionals		SC	Social Change
	IRS	International Reputation and Standards					S	Scholarship
	LE	Learning Environment						

Results and Discussion

In this section, the author presents the results of the dimensions of the study to determine the overall level of competitive advantage and non-competitive advantage of private universities in Mogadishu through analysis of statement strategies stated in the vision and mission posted on their official websites as well as a comparative analysis of the variance among them.

Table (3) Analysis of the vision and mission Statements for the Private Universities in Mogadishu

	Statement Strategies	Codes	Frequencies	Ratio %	Decision
Academic & Research (AR)	To be the premier university and distinguished institution.	PI	10	74.5	Non Competitive Advantage
	To provide high quality education.	QE	11	82	Non Competitive Advantage
	To provide high quality research.	QR	8	59.6	Non Competitive Advantage
	To improve abilities, skills, talents and creativities.	ASC	10	74.5	Non Competitive Advantage
	To strive for International reputation and standards	IRS	5	37.2	Competitive Advantage
	To improve the learning environment.	LE	4	30	Competitive Advantage
Value & Culture (VC)	To adhere to the national values and culture of the Somali people.	NV	3	22.3	Competitive Advantage
	To integrate social and Islamic values, scientific knowledge, and technical skills required for sustainable development of Somalia.	IV	2	15	Competitive Advantage
	To provide service to humanity.	H	4	30	Competitive Advantage
	To produce most ethical professionals.	EP	8	59.6	Non Competitive Advantage
Social Needs & Development (SND)	To provide community services	CS	11	82	Non Competitive Advantage
	To foster openness to a wide range of ideas.	OI	1	7.45	Competitive Advantage
	To produce generations committed to peace and good governance.	PG	2	15	Competitive Advantage
	To strive for change and to instill hope in the Somali society.	SC	2	15	Competitive Advantage
	To promote scholarship.	S	1	7.45	Competitive Advantage
Total			82	611.6	

Based on the objectives, and methodology of the study as a qualitative analysis of the statement strategies of visions and missions of the private universities in Mogadishu, table (3) illustrates the results of the three dimensions of the statement strategies of visions and missions viz.; (Academic & Research as coded (AR), Values & Culture coded (VC) and Social Needs and Development as coded (SND). The indicators of each dimension as presented in table one have been given codes and then were analyzed in QDA MINER.1.4.1. According to interval ratios and weights pre-established by the researcher that is (> 50% considered Non-competitive whereas < 50% considered as a Competitive advantage). For the dimension of Academic and Research, the results showed the statements of “To strive for International reputation and standards (IRS) 37.2%,” and “To improve the learning environment (LE) 30%” are

considered as Competitive advantages for the private universities in Mogadishu, while the ratio of the rest statements span 59.6% to 74.5, thus, they are considered non-competitive advantages.

For the dimension of Values and Culture as coded (VC), the results in a table(3)and figure (2) revealed that the statements “To adhere to the national values and culture of the Somali people (NV) 22.3%”, “To integrate social and Islamic values, scientific knowledge, and technical skills required for sustainable development of Somalia (IV) 15%” and “To provide service to humanity (H) 30%” are Competitive advantages and the statement “To produce most ethical professionals (EH) 59.6%” is non- competitive advantage for the private universities in Mogadishu.

The results of the dimension of Social needs and development (SND) contains five indicators; four of them are competitive advantages viz. “To foster openness to a wide

range of ideas (OI) 7.45%”, “To produce generations committed to peace and good governance (PG) 15%”, “To strive for change and to instil hope in the Somali society (SC) 15%” and “To promote scholarship(S) 7.45%” all these statement strategies are Competitive advantages. The statement “To provide community services (CS) 82% is merely non-competitive advantage of the private universities in Mogadishu.

Figure 4 below visualizes the overall ratio of competitive advantages and non-competitive advantages of the statement strategies contained in visions and missions of private universities in Mogadishu. Non-competitive advantages scored up 71% while competitive advantages recorded 29%.

Table 4. Analysis Matrix of Vision and Mission Indicators Related to the Dimension of Academic and Research

University	Academic and Research Indicators							Total	Mean
	PI	QE	QR	ASC	IRS	LE			
Mogadishu University-MU	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	5	11	
SIMAD University – SU	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	4	8.6	
Benadir University – BU	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	4	8.6	
Jazeera University – JU	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	4	8.6	
University of Somalia –UNISO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	4	8.6	
Jamhuriya University - JUST	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	5	11	
Somalia International University – SIU	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	4	8.6	
City University – CU	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	5	11	
Hormuud University HU	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	3	6.5	
Islamic University IU	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	4	8.6	
Plasma university –PU	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	4	8.6	
							46	100%	

Table (4) above and figure(5) below show the analysis matrix of private universities in Mogadishu and their vision and mission indicators related to the dimension of Academic and Research.

The results shown in the table and the figure reveal that Mogadishu University, Jamhuriya University, and City University scored up a top rank of 11% due to the availability of all the academic and research indicators in their vision and mission posted in their official website viz. premier institution (PI), quality of education (QE), quality research (QR), abilities, skills, and creativity (ASC), international reputation standards (IRS) and learning environment (LE). The second rank 8.6% gained by SIMAD University, Benadir University, Jazeera University, University of Somalia, Somalia International University, Islamic University, and Plasma University due to one or two indicators missing or not included overtly in their vision and mission. Hormuud University placed in the third rank with 6.5% due to three indicators are missing or not included obviously in its vision and mission. The results in the table and figure also show the indicator of the international reputation standards(IRS) is a competitive advantage for Mogadishu University, University of Somalia, Jamhuriya University, City University, and Plasma University, whereas the learning environment (LE) indicator is a competitive advantage for Mogadishu University, Benadir University, University of Somalia, and Hormuud University.

Table 5. Analysis Matrix of Vision and Mission Indicators Related to the Dimension of Values and Culture

University	Values and Culture Indicators					Total	Mean
	NV	IV	H	EP			
Mogadishu University-MU	YES	YES	NO	YES	3	17.6	
SIMAD University - SU	NO	NO	NO	YES	1	6	
Benadir University - BU	YES	NO	NO	YES	2	11.7	
Jazeera University - JU	NO	NO	YES	YES	2	11.7	
University of Somalia -UNISO	NO	NO	NO	NO	0	0	
Jamhuriya University - JUST	NO	NO	YES	NO	1	6	
Somalia International University -- SIU	NO	NO	NO	YES	1	6	
City University - CU	NO	NO	YES	YES	2	11.7	
Hormud Universi HU	NO	NO	NO	NO	0	0	
Islamic University IU	YES	YES	YES	YES	4	23.5	
Plasma university -PU	NO	NO	NO	YES	1	6	
					17	100%	

Table (5) and figure (6) present an analysis matrix of private universities in Mogadishu and their vision and mission indicators related to the dimension of values and culture.

The national value (NV) refers to a competitive advantage for Mogadishu University, Benadir University, and Islamic University. The Islamic values indicator (IV) is a competitive advantage merely for Mogadishu University and Islamic University. The humanity indicator (H) reflects only a competitive advantage to Jamhuriya University, Jazeera University, City University, and Islamic University. The means shown in the table and figure (6) demonstrate that Islamic University recorded the first rank of 23.5%, Mogadishu University obtained the second rank of 17.6%, and Benadir University, Jazeera University, and City University gained the third rank of 11.7%. SIMAD University, Jamahiriya University, Somalia International University, and Plasma University scored up the fourth rank of 6%. However, the University of

Somalia and Hormud University have no statement strategies of Values and culture indicators specified in their visions and missions.

Table 6. Analysis Matrix of Vision and Mission Indicators Related to the Dimension of Social Needs and Development

University	Social Needs and Development Indicators					Total	Mean
	CS	OI	PG	SC	S		
Mogadishu University-MU	YES	YES	YES	yes	NO	4	23.5
SIMAD University - SU	YES	NO	NO	no	NO	1	6
Benadir University - BU	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	3	17.6
Jazeera University - JU	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	2	11.7
University of Somalia -UNISO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
Jamhuriya University - JUST	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
Somalia International University -- SIU	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
City University - CU	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
Hormud Universi HU	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
Islamic University IU	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
Plasma university -PU	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	1	6
						17	100

The results presented in table (6) and figure (7) show all indicators –except community service (CS) are considered competitive advantages for three universities; Mogadishu University, Benadir University, and Jazeera University. Open ideas statement is only a competitive advantage for Mogadishu University, and the social change reflects vividly as a competitive advantage for both Benadir University and Mogadishu University whereas, the scholarship indicator refers to a competitive advantage for Jazeera University. The means illustrated in the table explored that Mogadishu University recorded the first rank of 23.5%, Benadir University obtained the second rank of 17.6%, and Jazeera University the third rank of 11.7% while the rest universities gained the fourth rank with the same value 6%.

Conclusion

Based on the objectives and the methodology of the study, the results revealed the level of vision and mission of the private universities in Mogadishu in achieving their competitive advantages. According to the dimensions, the content analysis was namely based on; Academic & Research, Ethics & Culture and Social Needs & Development, the overall percentage of competitive advantage and non-competitive advantage has been estimated; a competitive advantage was 29% whereas the non-competitive advantage logged 71%. The results demonstrated that the most indicators of non-competitive advantages concerted in the dimension of Academic and Research while competitive advantage indicators concentrated on the dimensions; Values & Culture and Social Needs with Development. The results of the study also explored the competitive advantage and non-competitive advantage variances among universities. Finally, the vision and mission of the eleven private universities in Mogadishu are consistent with the national vision and mission of the Somali Ministry for Education, Culture and Higher Education.

Recommendations

1. Private universities should review their vision and mission to keep up the pace with contemporary educational requirements in accordance with national and international standards.
2. National and Islamic values statements or items should be given a consideration to be included in the vision and mission for those universities not stated in their vision and mission.
3. Technology statement strategy should be stated overtly in the vision and mission of each university because of not specified clearly in the vision and mission statements.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that the study was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial interest. Thus, no competing interests exist.

Bibliography of the Author

Dr. Said Abubakar is an associate professor of education, curriculum at Mogadishu University, Somalia. His research areas include educational problems at all levels; primary, secondary and tertiary education as well as educational development viz. curriculum development, educational technology and teaching and learning strategies. Dr. Said Abubakar has educational articles published in Mogadishu University Journal and SERDEC Education Journal (SEJ). He is currently the head of research department at Mogadishu University.

References

- AchieveIt. (2014). The Link Between Mission , Vision , and Strategy Develop and Track Your Strategic Plans With AchieveIt ! *White Paper, 9001*, 1–2.
- Altiok, P. (2011). Applicable vision, mission and the effects of strategic management on crisis resolve. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 24, 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.09.057>
- Braslina, L., Viksne, K., Cumakovs, A., Batraga, A., & Braslina, L. (2014). *Economic Science for Rural Development No Innovative Competitive Advantage Determination Model*. 35(35), 34–42.
- Brătianu, c., & bălănescu, g. V. (2008). Vision , Mission and Corporate Values . A Comparative Analysis of the top 50 u . S . Companies Constantin BR Ă TIANU , Georgiana Victoria B Ă L Ă NESCU. *Management & Marketing*, 3(3), 19–38.
- BU. (2020, October,19). <https://bu.edu.so/history/Vision and Mission>. Retrieved from bu.edu.so/: <https://bu.edu.so/history/>
- CU. (2020, October,19). <http://www.cu.edu.so/about.html>. Retrieved from cu.edu.so: <http://www.cu.edu.so/visoin-mission--core-values.html>
- Diab, S. M. (2013). Using the Competitive Dimensions to Achieve Competitive advantage (A Study on Jordanian private hospitals). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(7), 138–150. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v3-i7/101>
- Dimitrova, G., & Dimitrova, T. (2017). Competitiveness of the universities: measurement capabilities. *Trakia Journal of Science*, 15(Suppl.1), 311–316. <https://doi.org/10.15547/tjs.2017.s.01.055>
- Heath, R. L., Johansen, W., & Bowen, S. A. (2018). Mission and Vision. *The International Encyclopedia of Strategic Communication*, January, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119010722.iesc0111>
- Hofstrand, D. (2016). Vision and Mission Statements -- a Roadmap of Where You Want to Go and How to Get There. *Iowa State University*, August.

www.extension.iastate.edu/agdm%0Ahttps://www.extension.iastate.edu/agdm/wholefarm/pdf/c5-09.pdf

- Horwath, R. (2005). Discovering purpose: Developing mission, vision. *Strategic Thinking Institute*.
- HU. (2020, October,19). [https://hu.edu.so/About HU](https://hu.edu.so/About%20HU). Retrieved from hu.edu.so: <https://hu.edu.so/about-hu/vision-mission/>
- IU. (2020, October,19). [https://islamicuniversity.so/en/About IU](https://islamicuniversity.so/en/About%20IU). Retrieved from <https://islamicuniversity.so/en/page/13/Vision-Mission-Objectives>.
- JU.(2020,October,19). <https://www.jazeerauniversity.com/Pagemenu/=6Pi8WcAHTOc1>. Retrieved from [jazeerauniversity.com/https://www.jazeerauniversity.com/Pagemenu/=6Pi8WcAHTOc1/Vision and Mission](https://www.jazeerauniversity.com/Pagemenu/=6Pi8WcAHTOc1/Vision%20and%20Mission)
- JUST. (2020, October,19). [https://just.edu.so/about JUST](https://just.edu.so/about%20JUST). Retrieved from just.edu.so/: <https://just.edu.so/vision-mission/>
- Kireeva, N., Slepenskova, E., Shipunova, T., & Iskandaryan, R. (2018). *Competitiveness of higher education institutions and academic entrepreneurship Competitividad en instituciones de educación superior y el emprendimiento académico*. 39(23).
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher education Somalia. (2017). *Federal Government of Somalia Ministry of Education , Culture and Higher Education Education Sector Analysis , 2012-2016. September, 2012–2016*.
- Mishra, C. S. (2017). Creating and sustaining competitive advantage: Management logics, business models, and entrepreneurial rent. In *Creating and Sustaining Competitive Advantage: Management Logics, Business Models, and Entrepreneurial Rent*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54540-0>
- MU. (2020, October,19). mu.edu.so/vision-mission/. Retrieved from mu.edu.so: <http://mu.edu.so/vision-mission/>
- Ozdem, G. (2011). An Analysis of the Mission and Vision Statements on the Strategic Plans of Higher Education Institutions. *Kuram Ve Uygulamada Egitim Bilimleri*, 11(4), 1887–1894.
- Pane, D. N., Fikri, M. EL, & Ritonga, H. M. (2018). No Title No Title. In *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* (Vol. 53, Issue 9).
- PU. (2020, October,19). <https://plasmauniversity.net/strategic-goals/>. Retrieved from plasmauniversity.net/: [https://plasmauniversity.net/strategic-goals/Vision and Mission](https://plasmauniversity.net/strategic-goals/Vision%20and%20Mission).
- SIU. (2020, October,19). <https://siu.edu.so/index.php/about-us/>. Retrieved from siu.edu.so/: [https://siu.edu.so/index.php/about-us/Vision and Mission](https://siu.edu.so/index.php/about-us/Vision%20and%20Mission).
- SU. (2020, October,19). <https://simad.edu.so/about-simad/>. Retrieved from simad.edu.so: [https://simad.edu.so/about-simad/Vision and Mission](https://simad.edu.so/about-simad/Vision%20and%20Mission).
- UNISO. (2020, Octobe,19). <https://www.uniso.edu.so/>. Retrieved from uniso.edu.so/